

Engineering project - ESTACA

Evaluation of unsteady aerodynamic regimes and their influence on the aerodynamic performance of a Formula Student front wing

Phase 1 tracking sheet

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Magenta = new parts

Acronyms

CFD : Computational Fluid Dynamics

GE : Ground Effect

Variables and Parameters

Non dimensional

C_L : Lift coefficient (—)

C_D : Drag coefficient (—)

Displacements

$z(t)$: Heave (m)

$\alpha(t)$: Pitch angle (rad)

Other

k : Turbulent Kinetic Energy

1. Objectives

Extract from the draft proposal:

Goal: Establish stable CFD setups and validate the baseline geometry.

1.1 Use of the S1223-IL airfoil, a high-lift profile commonly used in Formula Student for low Reynolds number applications.

1.1.1 Run a single-flap configuration in free air to understand basic flow characteristics.

1.1.2 Evaluate a single-flap configuration in ground effect to capture ground-induced pressure variations.

1.2 Parametrize a 3-element model

1.3 Simulate a three-element configuration (main element + 2 flaps) in ground effect to define reference aerodynamic coefficients. With DRS ON & OFF.

2. Single element model

To familiarize ourselves with the main simulation principles we first started with single element configurations: in free air and with ground effect.

Both s1223 configurations are run with the same inlet velocity: $v = 20 \text{ m/s}$, and angle of attack: 5° .

On the configuration with ground effect the ride height is 35mm.

According to the Formula Student regulations, the minimum ride height is **30 mm**, but we use **35 mm** in our simulations as a safety margin.

Velocity path lines Free air

Velocity path lines in Ground effect

The ground effect significantly enhances the downforce generated by the airfoil (higher C_l) by accelerating the flow beneath it, while causing a moderate increase in drag due to stronger viscous effects near the surface.

S1223	AoA ($^\circ$)	C_l	C_d
Ground effect	5	1,91	0,06
Free air	5	1,51	0,0326

3. Two element model

3.1. High downforce Design

For the two-element model, we have chosen to work on a wing composed of two flaps s1223.

To find the best design, the first step is to simulate multiple design with different parameters. We will modify the three following parameters:

- Angle of attack (second profile) ($^{\circ}$)
- overlap (mm)
- slot gap (mm)

The two following parameters will be constant:

- Angle of attack (first profil) (3°)
- Distance between first profil and the ground (35mm)

The method is to simulate 15 random positions and observe if there is a one or two better position than the other. Then we will do more simulation of the best position found with little position to optimise. Here are the 15 positions and the results simulated:

Position number	Angle of attack (second profil) ($^{\circ}$)	overlap (mm)	slotgap (mm)	Cl	Cd	efficiency
1	3	2	10	1.3	0.06	21.67
2	10	8	12.5	3.14	0.09	34.89
3	17	14	15	4.06	0.15	27.07
4	24	20	17.5	4.39	0.21	20.9
5	31	26	19	2.99	0.26	11.5
6	38	32	10	2.87	0.33	8.7
7	45	2	12	2.88	0.49	5.88
8	53	8	14.5	2.89	0.6	4.82
9	6.5	16	18	2.27	0.07	32.43
10	14.5	22	11	3.53	0.13	27.15
11	21.5	28	13.5	4.05	0.19	21.32
12	29	4.5	16	3.06	0.26	11.77
13	36.5	12.5	18.5	3.06	0.34	9
14	43.5	19.5	10.5	3.12	0.41	7.61
15	50	25	15.5	2.92	0.51	5.73

By comparing the value of the Cl, we notice that the position 4 has the best value with 4.39. We will therefore simulate our next positions around this one. Here are the value intervals used for the next 54 points:

Angle of attack (second profil)-> [13.5 ; 31] with a regular step of 3° (6 values)

overlap-> [16 ; 24] with a regular step of 4mm (3 values)

slot gap-> [15 ; 20] with a regular step of 2.5mm (3 values)

Point number	Angle of attack (second profil) (°)	overlap (mm)	slotgap (mm)	Cl	Cd	efficiency
16	13.5	16	15	3.65	0.12	30.42
17	13.5	16	17.5	3.61	0.12	30.08
18	13.5	16	20	3.56	0.12	29.67
19	13.5	20	15	3.59	0.12	29.92
20	13.5	20	17.5	3.58	0.12	29.83
21	13.5	20	20	3.54	0.12	29.5
22	13.5	24	15	3.53	0.12	29.42
23	13.5	24	17.5	3.52	0.12	29.33
24	13.5	24	20	3.49	0.12	29.08
25	17	16	15	4.04	0.15	26.93
26	17	16	17.5	3.99	0.15	26.6
27	17	16	20	3.94	0.14	28.14
28	17	20	15	3.94	0.15	26.27
29	17	20	17.5	3.99	0.14	28.5
30	17	20	20	3.89	0.14	27.79
31	17	24	15	3.89	0.15	25.93
32	17	24	17.5	3.88	0.14	27.71
33	17	24	20	3.81	0.14	27.21
34	20.5	16	15	4.38	0.17	25.76
35	20.5	16	17.5	4.32	0.17	25.41
36	20.5	16	20	4.19	0.17	24.65
37	20.5	20	15	4.2	0.18	23.33
38	20.5	20	17.5	4.23	0.18	23.5
39	20.5	20	20	4.15	0.17	24.41
40	20.5	24	15	4.06	0.19	21.37
41	20.5	24	17.5	4.12	0.17	24.24

42	20.5	24	20	4.03	0.17	23.71
43	24	16	15	4.56	0.22	20.73
44	24	16	17.5	4.49	0.2	22.45
45	24	16	20	2.79	0.2	13.95
46	24	20	15	4.44	0.22	20.18
4	24	20	17.5	4.39	0.21	20.9
47	24	20	20	3.16	0.18	17.56
48	24	24	15	4.31	0.21	20.52
49	24	24	17.5	4.29	0.2	21.45
50	24	24	20	3.58	0.17	21.06
51	27.5	16	15	4.65	0.26	17.88
52	27.5	16	17.5	2.84	0.23	12.35
53	27.5	16	20	3	0.24	12.5
54	27.5	20	15	4.56	0.26	17.54
55	27.5	20	17.5	3.1	0.22	14.09
56	27.5	20	20	2.92	0.23	12.7
57	27.5	24	15	4.4	0.25	17.6
58	27.5	24	17.5	2.88	0.23	12.52
59	27.5	24	20	3	0.22	13.64
60	31	16	15	3.09	0.28	11.04
61	31	16	17.5	3.11	0.27	11.52
62	31	16	20	3.09	0.27	11.44
63	31	20	15	3.1	0.27	11.48
64	31	20	17.5	3.1	0.27	11.48
65	31	20	20	3.06	0.27	11.33
66	31	24	15	3.09	0.27	11.44
67	31	24	17.5	3.08	0.26	11.85
68	31	24	20	3.03	0.26	11.65

In this new list of values, we can find position 4 and a list of points with little variation. The best value of Cl is 4.65 for position 51. This is the best point found for a maximization of the lift coefficient, but it doesn't have the best efficiency with 17.88. If the goal is to maximize this parameter, we could do another simulation of a list of positions around the position 2 that has the best efficiency with 34.89.

Visualization of the 54 positions simulated, colored by Cl

We can see that the parameter that influence the most the Cl is the flap angle

Velocity contour of the position 51

4. Three-element model

4.1. Design input

To save some precious time and focus on transient effects, we've chosen to start from a multi-element already designed: the ESTACA Formula Team's EC-05 Front Wing's multi-element.

This wing is composed of a main plane and two flaps, as follows:

- Main plane:
 - Selig S6063 low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 400mm chord
 - 2° angle of attack
- Flap 1:
 - Selig S1223 high lift low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 100mm chord
 - 24.55° angle of attack
- Flap 2:
 - Selig S1223 high lift low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 100mm chord
 - 34.55° angle of attack

However, the team is not fully confident about the angles of attack efficiency and the ability of the flow to stay attached under the flap's extrados, especially under extreme conditions (high pitch, high heave, ground clearance variations).

Therefore, we prefer to get an overview of the multi-element performance in 2D before considering it as a high-downforce baseline.

Once we are satisfied with a high-downforce baseline, we'll try to find the best low-drag configuration to set it as a baseline for the DRS.

4.2. High downforce baseline design

Since our main concern is the angle of attack of the elements, we have decided to first test the performance of the multi-element while reducing the angle of both flaps.

Then, we will check more precisely the flaps positioning in the x-direction (overlap) and z-direction (slot-gap)

To do that, we use the Ansys parametrization feature to run several simulations at once.

On the input, we have:

$C_l = 3.5$

$C_d = 0.3$

Efficiency = 11.7

4.2.1. Angles of attack determination explained

First, we want to get some general guidelines to know where to gain performance and reduce stalling.

So, we make several small parametrizations to explore the C_l variation across different angle setups.

The parameters are the following :

- Flaps angle (one rotation point for both flaps, on the leading edge of the first flap)
- Main-element angle (one rotation point for both flaps and main-element, on the leading edge of the main-element)
- Flap 2 angle (one rotation point for the second flap, on the leading edge of this flap)

For each simulation, we compare the C_l since it is our main concern for a high-downforce configuration.

To summarize, we try some flaps angles. With the best angle, we try some main-element angles. And with the best angle, we try some flap 2 angle. For each test we gather this in an Excel spreadsheet to have a better understanding of the results.

Figure 1 - Extract of the Excel Spreadsheet used for each test

One we have done all our tests, we gather all these in a 3D plot using Matlab.

With that 3D plot, we can then see in which region of parameters we would get the best performance, explore more precisely this area and choose a final setup.

Figure 2 - Extract of the Excel Spreadsheet used for the final choice. This is useful to see a particular test, like the determination of the flap 3 angle.

Figure 3 - Matlab 3D plot, useful to get an overview of the best "downforce areas"

4.2.2. Precise flaps positioning (Slot-gaps, Overlaps) explained

Once we have the best angle setup; we check whether the x and z-positioning of the flaps are the best.

4.2.2.1. Flap 1 and 2 positioning

To do that, we first run another parametrization on the first and second flap, moving in x and z. We gather the results in a plot, aiming for the best C_L .

Figure 4 - Parametrization on the first and second flap, moving in x and z.

In this plot (Fig. 4) the best configurations are near (-10; -10), however these configurations lead to a stall on flap 2, not visible in the number but very visible on the velocity contours.

That's why we decided to not go further and finally do the last parametrization on the second flap only moving the same way.

4.2.2.2. Flap 2 positioning

In a quick review of the different flap 2 positions, we see that the best configuration might be the current one (moving the flap in any direction does not generate any significant gain).

Figure 5 - Example: moving the flap in a z direction only provides 0.01 Cl. So, we choose to not lose more time and skip this parametrization

So, we choose to not go further on the x and z positioning but try to reduce the stalling by moving again the flap 2 angle of attack.

Unfortunately, this lowers the Cl, because the velocity near the leading edge is so powerful at high AoA that lowering the angle destroys the Cl. However, this brings us much more control and less turbulence in the wake of the multi-element.

4.2.3. Verification under extreme pitch and ground clearance variations.

During a brake test, the ESTACA Formula Team reportedly measured the following spring displacement:

Front: -4mm

Back: +5mm

With a wheelbase of 1588mm, this represents a pitch of $0.005668 \text{ rad} = 0.32^\circ$

The ground clearance variation reportedly very uncertain. The Team said it was a matter of millimetres.

So, we try different configurations:

- Brake test conditions

- -10mm of ground clearance
- +10mm of ground clearance

The purpose of this verification is to check whether there is any problem occurring at those specific events with this front wing design.

We expect to get different downforce values, but that's not really the point: we don't want any separation.

4.2.3.1. Brake test

We believe this test is not useful since the angle and ground clearance is minimal.

4.2.3.2. Ground clearance variation

Clearance lowered by 10 mm : $C_l = 4.00$

Figure 6 - C_pT contour at 20 m/s with the wing lowered by 10mm. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 7 - C_p contour at 20 m/s with the wing lowered by 10mm. Scale = [-6 ; 1]

Clearance increased by 10mm : $C_l = 4.47$

Figure 8 - C_pT contour at 20 m/s with the wing 10mm higher. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 9 - C_p contour at 20 m/s with the wing increased by 10mm. Scale = [-6 ; 1]

On both cases, the wing works. We note an augmentation of lift with the ground clearance. When the wing is up, the upwash is less powerful but the boundary layer is more powerful, which are expected phenomena due to the decrease of velocity under the wing.

Figure 10 - Cp graphs vs height

The Cp Graphs are consistent with the observations on the contours. The highest configuration generates more low pressure on every low-pressure surface, especially on the leading edge of the main element and on the first flap.

Also, we can notice that the main element endures less adverse pressure gradients, which can explain the wake angle decrease behind the wing.

4.2.4. Verification under various velocities.

We make a velocity sweep on this wing, from 5m/s to 35m/s, two borders very consistent with Formula Student extreme cases (very sharp corner, that is even always took with some yaw that we don't consider here, and very long straight)

The purpose of this verification is to check whether there is any problem occurring at those specific events with this front wing design.

We expect to get some similar Cl values for each case.

Results :

Figure 11 - Cl at different stream velocities

The results meet our expectations for the [15;30] range of velocities.

At $v = 5\text{m/s}$, the Cl value drops. Indeed, the flap 2 is stalling. This is something somewhat reassuring, as the S1223 is not strong enough to maintain the boundary layer at such low Reynolds ($Re = 33840$ on this flap!).

Figure 12 - Velocity contour at 5 m/s

Figure 13 - CpT contour at 5 m/s. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 14 - Cp contour at 5 m/s. Scale [-6; 1]

At $v = 10\text{m/s}$, the contours are very consistent with the other Reynolds cases. But the Boundary Layer is particularly thick because of the low speed (so low Re) as $\delta \propto 1/\sqrt{Re}$

This boundary layer thickness induces a boundary layer displacement that may be the cause of the augmentation of C_l in this case: the flow rate is the same but with a

reduced section, as the boundary layer thickens. So, the velocity rises, reducing pressure.

Figure 15 - Velocity contour at 10m/s

Figure 16 - CpT contour at 10 m/s. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 17 - Cp contour at 10 m/s. Scale [-6; 1]

At $v = 35\text{m/s}$, the contours are very consistent with the other Reynolds cases.

Figure 18 - Velocity contour at 35m/s

Figure 19 - CpT contour at 35 m/s. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 20 - Cp contour at 35 m/s. Scale [-6; 1]

Figure 21 - Cp graphs vs air velocity

The Cp-graphs also shows the clear evidence of stalling on $u = 5 \text{ m/s}$ on flap 1 and 2, led by high adverse pressure gradients on flap 1.

On $u = 10 \text{ m/s}$, the main element generates more low pressure underneath the airfoil, throughout the chord, probably thanks to the less powerful wake that generates less of a blockage behind the airfoil.

4.3. Low drag baseline

Difficult to find one since the rotation axle changes the flap disposition, but we aren't able to predict which one is the best.

May we assume that the best drag baseline is the configuration where the s1223 airfoil is the less draggy?

The less draggy angle would be around 1° for stable conditions

Blue: Re = 50.000

Orange: Re = 100.000

Yellow: Re = 200.000

Figure 22 - Cd vs AoA - from airfoiltools.com

4.4. Baseline results and numbers

4.4.1. High downforce configuration

- Main plane:
 - Selig S6063 low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 400mm chord
 - -1° angle of attack
- Flap 1:
 - Selig S1223 high lift low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 100mm chord
 - 10.55° angle of attack
 - Slot gap (+z): 26.35mm
 - Overlap (+x): 15.22mm
- Flap 2:
 - Selig S1223 high lift low Reynolds number airfoil
 - 100mm chord
 - 32.55° angle of attack
 - Slot gap (+z): 16mm
 - Overlap (+x): 18.67mm

Slot Gaps and Overlaps are the distance measured between the leading edge of the flap and the trailing edge of the predecessor.

The aerodynamic coefficients are:

$C_l = 4.252$

$C_d = 0.184$

Finesse = 23.109

Figure 23 - Velocity contour

Figure 24 - CpT contour at 20 m/s. Scale = [-0.6 ; 1]

Figure 25 - Cp contour at 20 m/s. Scale [-6; 1]

Compared to EC-05 configuration :

- C_l : +0.752 (+21.5%)
- C_d : -0.116 (-38.7%)
- Efficiency : +11.409 (+97.5%)

4.4.2. Low drag configuration

Not done yet, waiting for a fixed CFD case

5. Mesh study

5.1. Baseline

During this meshing study, we first created a baseline that will serve as our reference throughout our study. This required a perfect and precise baseline.

However, during our meshing, the TEs were very problematic with rapid compressions of our boundary layers.

We had to play around with the curvature parameters to obtain well-meshed TEs.

We reduced the minimum local size and decreased the possible angle between two meshes.

Figure 26 - Initial trailing edges

Figure 27 - Trailing edges refined

However, the leading edge of our flap was clean, it respected the shape of our geometry without having any guts. To achieve this, we carried out an iterative process until we obtained clean leading edges and trailing edges.

We refined our meshes on our Leading and trailing edge using curvature to accurately capture the normal gradient at the wall, but also the adjacent gradient, because the gradients are significant at the TE and LE.

As for the size of our cells on the upper and lower surfaces, we increased the width by decreasing the number of divisions on our edges but refined the boundary layers with a growth ratio of 1.1 to maintain an accurate resolution of normal gradients at the walls.

Figure 28 - Leading Edges

Figure 29- Full domain mesh

In addition, to maximize the accuracy of our results, we have implemented a BOI Near that will allow us to capture near-wall effect.

Meanwhile, the BOI Far will allow us to achieve good accuracy on the wake of our front wing

5.2. Analysis of the Effect of Cell Size Variation

Once we obtained and selected our baseline results, we conducted a series of tests. First, we attempted to multiply all mesh parameters (BOI and number of divisions) by factors of 2 and 3, and then performed the same tests by dividing them.

Next, we carried out a study on the influence of increasing and decreasing the BOI size alone, followed by the number of divisions, and obtained the following results:

Version	Nb of cells	Nb divisions Main	Nb divisions F1	Nb divisions F2	BOI NEAR(m)	BOI FAR(m)	DOMAIN(m)	Cd	Cl	Nb iterations	Iteration to converge	Residuals	Time
Baseline	104667	200	100	100	0,004	0,01	0,05	0,09	3,06	500	72	2*10 ⁻⁴	1 min 31
*2	36300	100	50	50	0,008	0,02	0,1	0,09	3,14	500	85	1*10 ⁻⁴	47 sec
*3	22650	66	33	33	0,012	0,03	0,15	0,09	3,12	500	141	1*10 ⁻⁵	32 sec
/2	348806	400	200	200	0,002	0,005	0,025	0,09	2,91	500	75	4*10 ⁻⁷	3 min 48
BOI /3 & Nb divisions Baseline	728963	200	100	100	0,00134	0,00333	0,0167	0,09	2,84	500	77	7*10 ⁻⁷	11 min 17
BOI Baseline & Nb division *2	101661	100	50	50	0,004	0,01	0,05	0,09	3,10	500	81	5*10 ⁻⁵	1 min 18
BOI * 2 & Nb division Baseline	42210	200	100	100	0,008	0,02	0,1	0,09	3,15	500	85	5*10 ⁻⁵	54 sec
BOI Baseline & Nb division /2	116379	400	200	200	0,004	0,01	0,05	0,09	3,01	500	72	5*10 ⁻⁷	1 min 58
BOI /2 & Nb division baseline	342484	200	100	100	0,002	0,005	0,025	0,09	2,90	500	71	5*10 ⁻⁵	3 min 42

Figure 30 - Table on Analysis of the Effect of Cell Size Variation

5.2.1. Global mesh scaling

As we can see from the results:

Coarser meshes ($\times 2$, $\times 3$) led to a significant reduction in cell count and runtime, while maintaining nearly identical aerodynamic coefficients.

- For example, the $\times 3$ case reached residuals of 1×10^{-5} in only 32 seconds, with $Cd = 0.089$ and $Cl = 3.12$ — a negligible deviation from the baseline.

Finer meshes ($\div 2$) produced much lower residuals ($\approx 4 \times 10^{-7}$), but Cd and Cl remained unchanged.

5.2.2. Influence of BOI

- Reducing the cells of BOI drastically increased the cell count and computation time (11 minutes).
 - Although residuals dropped to 10^{-7} , the aerodynamic coefficients changed by less than 2%.
 - This indicates that BOI refinement increases numerical cost disproportionately to accuracy gains.

5.2.3. Influence of divisions

- Adjusting the number of divisions has a moderate impact on runtime and convergence.
- Doubling the divisions slightly reduced residuals (5×10^{-5}) and stabilized convergence without significantly increasing cost.
 - Halving them yielded similar Cd/Cl results with slightly lower residuals ($\approx 5 \times 10^{-7}$).

After all this, we therefore believe that the best solution would be to have a BOI that is half as thin but to keep the initial number of divisions.

5.3 Mesh validation

To validate the model we use, we decided to test a NACA 0012, a basic airfoil, under ground-effect conditions and correlate our results with experimental data.

We decided to use the K-omega SST model, aiming for $y^+ \sim 1$.

The choice of NACA 0012 was made because of the number of experimental studies made with this airfoil. The simulation has been run with an h/c ratio of 0.2

Figure 23 - C_p Experimental

Figure 24 - C_p Numerical

The numerical pressure coefficient distribution $C_p(x/c)$ obtained from the Fluent simulation was compared with the experimental reference data on both the upper and lower surfaces of the airfoil. Overall, both curves exhibit the same characteristic aerodynamic behavior, which validates the physical consistency of the simulation.

The local minimum on the lower surface is located at approximately $x/c = 0.3$ on both the numerical and experimental curves:

The CFD result on that point gives a value of $C_p \approx -0.83$, while the experimental data indicates a slightly lower depression of $C_p \approx -0.79$. The corresponding relative error can be quantified as:

$$\text{Relative Error(\%)} = \left| \frac{-0.83 - (-0.79)}{-0.79} \right| \times 100 = \left| \frac{-0.04}{-0.79} \right| \times 100 \approx 5.06\%$$

Moreover, the experimental results yield a lift coefficient of $C_L = 0.26$. Under the same conditions, the CFD calculation predicts $C_L = 0.251$. The corresponding relative deviation is:

$$\text{Relative Error(\%)} = \left| \frac{0.251 - 0.26}{0.26} \right| \times 100 \approx 3.46\%$$

This very small difference, in the order of only 3.5%, demonstrates a strong agreement between the numerical model and the experimental data. Considering typical uncertainties related to ground-effect aerodynamics, tunnel-wall interactions, and turbulence modelling, the CFD prediction can be regarded as highly reliable.

After performing several simulations to test the mesh with an angle of 0° , we then varied the flap angle of attack to observe how the mesh behaves. A test was therefore carried out for angles ranging from -5° to 10° .

Figure 32 - C_L with angle variation Numerical

Figure 31 - C_L with angle variation Experimental

In this figure, the curve of interest is the pink one, corresponding to an h/c value of 0.2.

Based on the results, a larger difference compared to the 0° case can be observed. However, this deviation remains within acceptable limits.

Consequently, the mesh is considered validated.

6. Case used for 2D CFDs

6.1. Turbulence model choice

We must make sure to use the most consistent turbulence model for our 2D simulations. However, we lack real-world results to correlate and approach the real phenomena with a turbulence model and its right mesh. So, we will rely on literature and some criteria to choose our model. We shortlisted the following models:

- **K- ω SST ($y^+ \sim 1$)**
- **Spalart-Almaras ($y^+ \sim 1$)**

By trying a model not fully solved but using wall functions ($y^+ > 30$), we would save a lot of computation time, heavily important for future transient simulations.

But wall functions are weak in predicting stalling, huge pressure gradients and precise fluctuations. So, we might lose too much of accuracy and this is why we decided to not use it for this study.

K- ω SST w/ $y^+ \sim 1$ is the most common used in motorsport and seems to be the most suitable in our case, for its ability to compute and capture accurately the near-wall phenomena, that are extremely important in ground-effect conditions, where the airfoil performance is very sensitive to those phenomena and APG (adverse pressure gradients). In transient conditions, the pressure gradients will be essential, so the ω will be essential in this case

Spalart-Almaras' model is vastly used in aeronautic and industrial automotive applications because of its efficiency – or cheapness. However, with its only equation that relies on turbulent viscosity – and not energy dissipation, it predicts poorly the flow behavior in separated or critical regions.

The test has been made with the NACA0012, for the same reasons as detailed in 5.3.

6.1.1.K- ω SST

The C_L computed is $C_L = 0.251$ as written previously. The computation time is consequent even if it is still quite low.

Figure 33 - y^+ on NACA 0012 with $k-\omega$ SST

Figure 34 - C_p vs x/c on $k-\omega$ SST and experimental data

6.1.2. Spalart-Almaras

For this simulation, we've computed a C_L of 0.263. This is closer than the experimental data from

Figure 17 - y^+ on NACA 0012 with S-A

Figure 18 - C_p vs. x/c with S-A and experimental data

Furthermore, since it was predicted, the computation time has been heavily reduced. However, the computation is quite unstable, even if the results fully converged. This is visible on the residuals:

Figure 35 - Residuals on S-A simulation

This good C_L is to balance with this instability and the fact that on this NACA0012 in steady state, everything is happening smoothly: no separation nor heavy APG. So, we're in perfect condition for S-A but that do not really match the reality of our transient experiment.

6.1.3. Conclusion

The conclusion is quite hard to take as Spalart-Almaras' model shows some interesting points: the computation is quicker and closer to reality in this steady state and smooth case.

But what would it be in more difficult conditions? Sadly, we don't have any comparison point and it is incredibly hard to find one.

Therefore, we decided to trust global opinion and stay on K- ω SST model. Eventually, once we'll be on transient studies, we will compare again the two models.

6.2. Mesh

$y^+ \sim 1$ mesh.

Same strategy as previously detailed.

The wing is at 50mm from the ground with the configuration detailed in 4).

Figure 36 - Mesh used and y^+ plot on the wing. K-omega SST Model

6.3. Boundary conditions

Enveloppe: 3c in front, 9c behind and 5c over the wing. (c = chord).

Fluid: Air in ISA conditions:

Temperature = 15°C

Density = 1.225 kg/m³

Kinematic viscosity: 14.61E-6 m²/s

Inlet: velocity inlet

Velocity: 20 m/s

Turbulence: 5% of intensity, 10 of viscosity ratio (Ansys default)

Outlet: pressure outlet

We shouldn't have any backflow.

Upper wall: static, with no shear (slip) and no roughness

Floor: moving at 20m/s

Roughness height at 0.5mm and a roughness constant at 0.5 (Ansys default)

Flaps: static, nothing special

6.4. Solving

All the CFDs are solved on ANSYS Fluent since it is the commercial CFD solver provided by the ESTACA.

Fluent is in Double Precision and calculated on 4 CPU cores.

We assume the case to be incompressible: the solving is pressure-based. For the moment, we are still in steady state and 2D Planar.

We don't put any convergence criteria on the residuals and force reports (Cl, Cd) for the moment. It may be necessary to save some computational time during transient cases.

Solving method: Coupled, discretizations in second order.

Initialization: hybrid (10 iterations). Aiming for 10^{-7}

Calculation: 100 to 500 iterations in steady state, to reach total convergence (cl, cd and residuals)